

1 **Immunoglobulin-based therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis:**
2 **CYP3A43.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the liver is a frequent complication
8 of both breast cancer and colorectal cancer, among the two most common cancers that afflict man (1-5).
9 We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially
10 expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to
11 the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to conduct drug discovery by
12 measuring total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with breast cancer, comparing the liver
13 metastatic transcriptome to the primary tumor transcriptome. We identify here a therapeutic target based
14 on its differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the liver, CYP3A43, as a candidate
15 therapeutic target for the medical management of liver metastasis using immunoglobulin-based reagents.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, “regional” metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the liver metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: CYP3A43.

Results

Figure 1: CYP3A43 is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Liver metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=19 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=16 liver metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
211442_x_at	4.88E-03	-2.996605	-2.33049	-1.7007246	CYP3A43	352/22283	98.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in liver metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of *CYP3A43* in metastasis to the liver in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *CYP3A43* changed more than 98% of the human liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,283 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *CYP3A43* messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *CYP3A43* during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Liver metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=19 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=27 liver metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100143630_TGI_at	1.01E-02	-2.68	-2.949395	-9.33E-01	CYP3A43	3356/52378	93.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in liver metastases of humans with breast cancer (10), we validated differential expression of cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 43, encoded by *CYP3A43* in metastasis to the liver in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of *CYP3A43* changed more than nearly 95% of the human liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 52,378 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *CYP3A43* messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *CYP3A43* during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

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Thus, differential and increased expression of CYP3A43 defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Immunoglobulin-based inhibitors of CYP3A43, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are predicted to be at high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

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Methods

We utilized GSE124647 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.